

STRAIN MEASUREMENT AND INVESTIGATION OF THE CONCRETE QUALITY UNIFORMITY OF A BORED PILE FOUNDATION USING FIBER OPTIC SENSORS UNDER STATIC LOAD TEST

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ABSTRACT: Bored pile foundation is used to transfer structural load to soils. The construction method is by drilling the soils up to the designed layer, rebars inserted and concrete poured using tremie method. The possible imperfection in pouring concrete is difficult to detect but could lead to low bearing capacity of the foundation. To obtain a quality bored pile and ascertain its bearing capacity is a must.

In this study the load distribution and concrete quality were investigated utilizing fiber optic sensors to transmit information along the bored pile continuously at interval 5 cm. The fiber optic cables were installed at four sides in the bored pile. The maximum test load was 200% design load as ASTM requirements. However, sudden failure occurred while the test load increased up to 100% design load. The bored pile was 1000 mm in diameter, 36.35 m long and the 100% design load was 600 tons. Large strains were detected at depth of 3 to 6 m below the ground surface. Investigation on the cause of failures were then conducted based on worksite informations. A 3D FEM analysis numerical investigation was also done. The strains measured by fibre optic cables were able to detect the position of bad concrete and the result of the FEM study conclude that the test load was transferred to the soils mainly at the upper layer which clearly showed very high strains. The bored pile was then manually excavated to investigate the concrete visually. It is confirmed that the failure was on the structural part. Repair was conducted. The pile then retested without the fibre optic cables that were already damaged. This study concludes that fibre optic sensors instrument capable to measure the strain continuously during load test and to evaluate the load transfer, as well as the pile integrity and quality.

Keywords: concrete quality, uniformity, bored pile foundation, fiber optic sensors, static load test

INTRODUCTION

To confirm the bearing capacity of bored piles in a project located at Bumi Serpong Damai (BSD) consisting three towers of 30 stories, two (2) load tests were carried out which were instrumented by fibre optic sensors. The bored piles dimension was 1000 mm in diameter and 30 m length. The design load was 600 tons, while Kentledge system was prepared for load 1200 tons.

Two main objectives of bored pile load test were: to prove that the bearing capacity of the bored pile meet the minimum 200% design load according to ASTM, as well as to investigate the

characteristic of the transfer of load along the length of the bored pile. Since the fibre optic cable is capable to transmit information at close interval (5-10 cm), the other goals that also able to be investigated were integrity and homogeneity of the bored pile material. If the quality of the concrete is bad or highly varied, the fibre optic sensors could detect those situations based on the strain value at each location. Of course the opinion from the expert is important for interpretation of the test results.

DISTRIBUTED FIBRE OPTIC SENSOR TECHNOLOGY

To determine the load distribution characteristic along the pile shaft, Brillouin Optical Time Domain Analysis (BOTDA) system was used. The BOTDA system uses two different light sources, launched from two ends of an optical circuit. The system utilizes the backward stimulated Brillouin scattering (SBS); i.e., the pumping pulse light launched at one end of the fiber and propagates in the fiber, while the continuous wave (CW) light is launched at the opposite end of the fiber and propagates in the opposite direction, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Principle Measurement of BOTDA System (after Mohamad and Tee, 2015)

In this configuration, the pump pulse generates backward Brillouin gain whereas the CW light interacts (amplifies) with the pump pulse light to create stimulated Brillouin scattering. The Brillouin frequency shift in the single mode fiber is proportional to the change in the strain or temperature of that scattering location. By resolving this frequency shifts and the propagation time, a full strain profile along the pile can be obtained.

CHRONOLOGY OF THE BORED PILE INSTALLATION

The preparation for bored pile installation basically follow those commonly practiced in Indonesia. The drilling was done using auger to reach the bottom of the soils with sufficient bearing capacity. Prior to concrete pouring, base cleaning was conducted and also fibre optic was installed at the rebars. This pile was designed as friction piles and hence the quality of the drilling holes is very important. Figure 2 shows the fiber optic equipment set and their installation in the pile. Due to the planning of excavation for basement, the friction of the upper part were normally avoided of reduced using geo-gundle.

SOIL CONDITION

Based on soil investigation data, the soil condition can generally be divided into 4 soil layers. The first layer is a reddish clay with thickness of about 8 m ($N_{SPT} = 2 - 4$ blows/ft). Underlying layer

is a silty clay with thickness of about 2 m ($N_{SPT} = 19 - 24$ blows/ft). The third layer is cemented sand with gravel ($N_{SPT} > 50$ blows/ft) located at about 10 m to 24.5 m depth. The fourth layer is a silty clay layer ($N_{SPT} = 14 - 28$ blows/ft) located at 24.5 depth until the end of boring. Figure 4 shows the soil stratification in the project site.

Figure 2. Set of fiber optic equipment (a) and Fiber Optic Installation (b)

Figure 3. Trouble on Pulling Out the Pile Casing during Concreting

Figure 4. Soil Condition on Project Site

LOAD TEST PROCEDURES AND MEASUREMENTS

The axial static loading test was conducted based on ASTM D1143-07 with Kentledge system. One hydraulic jack with capacity of 2000 tons were used to produce load to the test pile. During loading phase, the load is controlled with pressure gauges, which is located in the hydraulic jack.

The design load of the test pile is 600 tons and loaded in five cycles as follows:

Table 1. Plan of Load Cycle for the Test Pile

Cycle	Max Load (%)	Max. Load (tons)
1	50	300
2	100	600
3	150	900
4	200	1200
5	250	1500

LOADING TEST RESULTS

The loading test on the instrumented pile did not run as planned, which were stopped at the third cycle. At load of 150% (900 tons), the pile top movement was highly increased. The load-settlement curve of the pile is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Result of Load Test (5 Cycles)

As can be seen from the results, the residual settlement of pile is relatively small, which means that the pile is still under elastic condition. However, during cycle 3 (100%-150% load), the pile top movement highly drops and the test was terminated immediately. It was expected either failures were due to lack of bearing capacity or structural failures. Hence investigation was proposed to study the mechanism of failure.

FIBRE OPTIC MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The fiber optic cables were installed along the reinforcement bars, inside the stirrups of the bored pile. The strain profile at each line are shown in Figure 6. The negative strain value indicates the pile condition is under "compression", while the positive value indicates the pile condition is under "tension". These negative strain values will be elaborated and explained in the next section.

Figure 6. Strain Profile Obtained at Each Side (Cycle 2: 100% Load)

Figure 7. Orientation of Bad Concrete Based on Measured Strain Data

From these results, there are indications of bad concrete showed by the high values of strain ($-3000 \mu\epsilon$). The existence of bad concrete is about at the depth of 3 to 6 m. Moreover, negative values of strain are also shown in the pile, which is very unusual and unlikely to happen in the pile. Because of these reasons, an excavation conducted to 6 m below the ground surface in order to check the condition of the pile. The excavation clearly gives the confirmation that there is a defect in the pile at the depth of 3 to 6 m, as same as indicated by the fiber optic. Figure 7 clearly shows the position of the defect at the pile.

Figure 8. Excavation and visual defect investigation

INTERPRETATION OF CONCRETE QUALITY FROM LOAD TEST RESULTS

The pouring phase of concrete mix for deep bored piles foundation often encounters a specific casting situation where the end of the concrete mix pipe is below the groundwater level. In such situation concrete pouring is done by using tremie system so that the concrete never mixed with ground water. Therefore, the tip of the concrete pipe may not be lifted out of the surface of the concrete mix that has been casted. However, to guarantee the safety of the upper structures held by the bored pile, it is required that a series of load tests should be carried out on the bored pile.

In this project fiber optic sensors were used to monitor and record the concrete strain that arises during the static load test stages. The large strains recorded and accumulated at a bored pile along the depth of 3 to 6 meters lead to doubts that the quality of the bored pile concrete was not achieved. But to ensure that disassembly actions must be performed, verification is done by 3D FEM analysis.

INVESTIGATION OF BORED PILE QUALITY USING FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

In order to simulate the loading test and failure mechanism in the pile, 3D model constructed using finite-element based program, MIDAS GTS NX. The soils and the pile are modeled with solid elements, using Mohr-Coulomb soil model. The Mohr-Coulomb soil model on pile is selected rather than linear elastic model in order to simulate the failure of the pile. The defect of the pile is also modeled as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. 3D Finite Element Model of the Pile Load Test

After creating the 3D Model of pile and soils, the calculation then conducted with stage construction. The stage are as follows:

1. Initial condition, which is the self-weight analysis for calculating the initial stress condition of the soils.
2. Install the pile with a defect. The defect is specified as bad concrete, which has elastic modulus much less than normal concrete's.
3. Apply the test load of 600 tons (without following the load cycle). The cyclic loading in this study is considered unnecessary.

Figure 10. Result of FEM Analysis: Strain Profile at Each Side

As can be seen in the figure, the strain profile obtained from the model relatively gives the same profile as the measured strain in the field, especially on side A. This result gives a sufficient approximation that the bad concrete in the pile has inclined orientation.

DISCUSSIONS

Casting of concrete for foundation of bored piles usually encountered the difficult situation of casting of concrete mixture under surface water table. Based on soil investigation, all of the drillings show consistency where cemented sands were found and previous load test has been carried out successfully. The results of fiber concrete data and the finite element analysis confirm that bad concrete was the main factor that contribute to the failure of the test. Fiber concrete measured continuously the strains along the pile length and high strain may be interpreted as low quality concrete (i.e low moduli).

CONCLUSIONS

Record from continuous strain measurement by fiber optic sensing is very beneficial for interpretation of the overall behavior of boredpiles during load test. Concrete quality may be interpreted more accurately not only the structural capacity but also location of bad concrete if any. By knowing the location of the defect accurately, it enable to determine the best alternative for precise repair. If the location of the defect is near ground surface, it is easier to dig to the depth and cover it with better concrete quality, however if the location of the defect is deep beyond ground surface, then grouting is better recommended.

SPECIAL QUOTE

Because the success or failure of building lies buried deep with the foundations, we ignore them. But if we do, then like a child that grows up and turns round to disappoint us with their behaviour so will the foundations when we build without forethought and diligence to the ground and materials we use. **Karl Terzaghi (1883-1963†)**

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